

ENERGY-SAVING MODES OF CONCRETE HEAT TREATMENT

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Abstract. *The article presents the results of studies of the influence of environment temperature on the modes of heat treatment of concrete. The method of assigning the modes of heat treatment of concrete, taking into account the temperature of the hot climate, is proposed.*

Keywords: *hot climate, concrete, concrete heat treatment method, concrete hardening, temperature gradient.*

A number of key resolutions have been adopted in the Republic of Uzbekistan aimed at improving energy efficiency in the sectors of the economy and the social sphere, introducing energy-efficient and energy-saving technologies, further developing renewable energy, and ensuring the rational use of energy resources.

The precast concrete industry is one of the largest consumers of energy among other sectors of the national economy.

Currently, an integral and at the same time the longest process in the production of precast concrete is heat treatment.

Despite certain successes, heat treatment has been and remains the longest technological stage in the production of precast concrete, taking 80-90% of the total time required for the manufacture of products.

The main advantage of steam heating is the possibility of providing favorable humidity conditions for concrete hardening, when the steam is in direct contact with the unformed surface of the products. The widespread use of steam heating in the production of prefabricated reinforced concrete in our country and abroad is explained not so much by the merits of the method as by its thorough knowledge and extensive practical experience.

To accelerate the hardening of concrete in prefabricated structures, heat treatment with steam has been used since the beginning of the last century.

Numerous studies have been and are being carried out on this issue and the method is well described in a number of works by S.A. Mironov, L.A. Malinina and B.A. Krylov [4,6,7,8].

Depending on the adopted manufacturing technology, the conditions for heat treatment of products change: concrete is heated either through the metal of the mold, or by direct contact of the product with the coolant. In this regard, the question arose about the processing of optimal steaming modes in relation to specific production conditions. Starting from the mid-1950s and to this day, extensive studies have been

and are being carried out on the effect of elevated hardening temperatures on the phase composition, the structure of neoplasms, the degree of hydration of the binder, and the exotherm of cement.

A great contribution to the problem was made by the international conference RILEM, held in 1964 in Moscow. A number of reports were made at it on the issue of choosing cement for heat treatment [3,10], the processes of hydration of Portland cement during heat treatment [1,9,13], reducing the hardening time of concrete [2,5,11], temperature gradients in concrete subjected to steaming and hardening of concrete in the conditions of Central Asia [12].

In a hot climate, a high outdoor temperature (30 ... 35 °C) is observed 6 ... 7 months a year. Under such conditions, the temperature of the concrete mixture at the moment of molding reaches 25 ... 30 °C. However, at present, these factors are not taken into account when assigning concrete heat treatment modes; as a result, the duration of heat treatment and energy consumption at enterprises in the southern and northern regions remain the same.

In order to study the influence of the initial temperature of the concrete mixture and the ambient temperature on the modes of heat treatment of concrete, we carried out a number of studies.

The research results showed that the initial temperature of the concrete mixture significantly affects the nature of the increase in the strength of concrete.

Thus, the preliminary curing of concrete on Portland cement at a relatively high ambient temperature, on the one hand, leads to a reduction in the preliminary curing time, an increase in the strength of concrete immediately after heat treatment, and on the other hand, a slowdown in further hydration of Portland cement after heat treatment.

As a result, by the end of the heat treatment, concrete with an increased initial temperature gains a greater amount of degree-hours compared to concrete with a lower initial temperature and, accordingly, the strength indicators are 70 and 61% of R_{28nt}.

From the foregoing, it follows that an elevated ambient temperature has a beneficial effect on the individual stages of heat treatment. With an increase in ambient temperature, the initial temperature of the concrete mixture increases, which, at the same rate of temperature rise, helps to reduce the time of this stage compared to concrete having a lower initial temperature. The cooling of the concrete is slower due to the decrease in the temperature gradient between the concrete and the environment, thus it is possible to reduce the isothermal holding time.

Thus, the results of experimental studies prove the correctness of the assumptions on reducing the isothermal holding time during the heat treatment of concrete in hot climates. The purpose of heat treatment modes for each specific case, depending on the initial temperature of the concrete and the environment, requires special study. This is a labor-intensive process, takes a considerable amount of time and is extremely inconvenient (and in many cases generally unacceptable) for production workers.

Therefore, we proposed an analytical method for optimizing the modes of keeping products during heat treatment, taking into account the temperature of the medium.

The increased initial temperature (25...30°C) prior to heat treatment contributes to a more intensive increase in the strength of concretes prepared with Portland cement during heat treatment.

The strength of concrete prepared with Portland cement is significantly affected by the nature of cooling; cooling at an elevated temperature (35-40°C) of the environment proceeds more slowly, reduces temperature gradients in the product, and contributes to an increase in the strength of concrete immediately after heat treatment.

The appointment of heat treatment modes for prefabricated reinforced concrete products, taking into account the ambient temperature of a hot climate, makes it possible to reduce the time of the active cycle (temperature rise + isothermal heating) by 2 ... 3 hours. The reduction in energy costs is 20 ... 22%.

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